

Why That Robot? A Qualitative Analysis of Justification Strategies for Robot Color Selection Across Occupational Contexts

Appendix

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I. VISUAL STIMULI AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Figure 1 illustrates the experimental workflow for Study 1 and Study 2, including the four task scenarios and the stereotype versus non-stereotype priming manipulations used in Study 2. Figure 2 presents the complete robot stimulus set: six color options (Light, Medium, Brown, Dark, Silver, Teal) crossed with five human-likeness levels.

Fig. 1. Experimental procedure and task scenarios for Study 1 (no human priming) and Study 2 (stereotype and non-stereotype priming conditions).

Fig. 2. Complete robot stimulus set, including Silver and Teal non-skin-tone baselines and the four skin-tone options (Light, Medium, Brown, Dark) at each of the five human-likeness levels.

II. AI CODING SYSTEM INSTRUCTION AND EMBEDDED CODEBOOK

To ensure replicability, we present the exact system instruction supplied to the language model during the AI-assisted coding phase. This instruction combines coding rules with the complete multidimensional codebook. During the coding procedure, each participant's open-ended justification was iteratively passed to the model within the prompt template: Participant's reason for choosing the robot: ``...``. The system prompt is reproduced below in markdown format.

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You are an expert qualitative data coder.
You will be provided with a reason given by a participant for selecting a robot from a set
of robots with different colors.
Your task is to assign exactly ONE main category and ONE sub-category from the provided
codebook under the main category you assigned.
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Carefully read the given reason, analyze its meaning, and pick the best fitting category
and sub-category.
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Codebook:
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## Category 1: Functionalism & Task-Fit
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Justifications based on the robot's perceived ability to perform the specific job
effectively based on its physical appearance.
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| Sub-Code | Definition | Key Keywords / Examples |
| :--- | :--- | :--- |
| **1.1 Durability & Ruggedness** | Belief that the robot's color/build indicates physical
strength or resistance to damage. | "Tough," "strong," "rugged," "sturdy," "heavy-duty,"
"withstand wear-and-tear." |
| **1.2 Cleanliness & Maintenance** | Focus on how the robot interacts with the
environment's cleanliness (hiding dirt or appearing sterile). | "Hide dirt," "camouflage
with mud," "looks clean," "sterile," "medical," "hygiene." |
| **1.3 Visibility & Safety** | The practical need for the robot to be seen by humans to
prevent accidents or for easy tracking. | "Stand out," "easy to spot," "high visibility,"
"safety," "hard to miss," "not blend in." |
| **1.4 Professionalism & Contextual Fit** | Matching the "unwritten rules" or typical
uniforms of a specific industry or The robot's appearance matches the environment or the
"uniform" of the job. | "Medical scrubs," "lab coats," "looks like an engineer,"
"professional," "suited for the task." matches the environment or the "uniform" of the
job."Suit the decoration," |
| **1.5 Performance/Capability** | General attribution of skill, accuracy, or efficiency
based on appearance. | "Capable," "efficient," "precise," "advanced sensors," "reliable,"
"athletic." |
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## Category 2: Psychological & Affective Impact
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Justifications based on the emotional response the robot elicits in the user or the target
audience (patients, students, athletes).
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| Sub-Code | Definition | Key Keywords / Examples |
| :--- | :--- | :--- |
| **2.1 Approachability & Trust** | Perception of the robot as non-threatening, kind, or
welcoming to humans. | "Friendly," "soothing," "disarming," "calm," "non-intimidating,"
"not scary." |
| **2.2 Engagement & Animation** | Belief that bright or "fun" colors will motivate users
or keep their attention. | "Engaging," "appeal to kids," "happy," "vibrant," "cheery,"
"not boring." |
| **2.3 Human-Likeness (Social)** | Explicitly choosing a robot because it looks "more
human" or has a "skin tone" appropriate for social interaction. | "Looks like a person,"
"more human," "bedside manner," "relatable." |
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## Category 3: Machine-Centric Heuristics
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Justifications that emphasize the robot's status as an industrial tool, often to avoid
social or racial complications.
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| Sub-Code | Definition | Key Keywords / Examples |
| :--- | :--- | :--- |
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| **3.1 Materiality & Industrialism** | Associating colors with raw materials like metal,
steel, or plastic. | "Looks like metal," "made of steel," "utilitarian," "machinery,"
"silver/grey is a robot color." |
| **3.2 Neutrality & De-racialization** | Explicitly stating that robots should not have
human skin tones or choosing a color to be "neutral." | "Neutral shade," "robots shouldn't
have race," "least reaction," "unnatural color." |
| **3.3 Anti-Distraction** | Choosing a "boring" or "basic" color so the user focuses on
the task, not the robot. | "Non-distracting," "unnoticed," "basic," "won't
over-stimulate." |

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## Category 4: Preference & Evasion
Low-effort or purely subjective justifications.

| Sub-Code | Definition | Key Keywords / Examples |
| :--- | :--- | :--- |
| **4.1 Personal Aesthetic** | Simple statements of personal liking or attraction to a
color. | "I like the color," "it's my favorite," "attractive," "caught my eye." |
| **4.2 Random/Equivalence** | Admitting the choice was arbitrary or that all robots
seemed identical. | "Randomly picked," "no reason," "they all look the same," "just picked
one." |

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## Category 5: Identity & Social Mapping
Justifications that reveal underlying social mapping or identity projection.

| Sub-Code | Definition | Key Keywords / Examples |
| :--- | :--- | :--- |
| **5.1 Stereotype Alignment** | Choosing the based on the participant's belief that the
chosen color matches the typical, common, or expected human demographic of a specific
profession. | I think the color white may imply it's smart? Like the way you assume people
in white lab coats are smart. |
| **5.2 Identity Projection** | participant chooses a robot specifically because it
mirrors their own personal characteristics, | It's just a reflection of myself. |

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III. DETAILED CATEGORY EXPLANATIONS AND REPRESENTATIVE EXAMPLES

This section provides expanded explanations and representative participant quotes for each of the five main categories and fifteen sub-categories used in the qualitative coding of robot color selection justifications. Examples are drawn from diverse task contexts (construction, hospital, tutoring, sports), participant racial backgrounds (Asian, Black/African American, Latino/Hispanic, White), and robot human-likeness levels to illustrate the full breadth of reasoning patterns identified in RQ1. Each quote is annotated with the participant's race, the robot color selected, the task context, and the human-likeness level (L1–L5).

A. Category 1: Functionalism

Justifications in this category are grounded in the robot's perceived ability to perform a specific job effectively based on its physical appearance. Participants drew on practical reasoning about how a robot's color relates to durability, cleanliness, visibility, professionalism, or general capability within a given occupational context. This was the most prevalent category, accounting for 53.0% of all responses.

a) *1.1 Durability & Ruggedness* ($N = 212$, 3.6%): Participants believed the robot's color or build indicated physical strength or resistance to damage. This sub-category was most prominent in construction (10.1% of construction responses) and sports contexts, where physical demands made ruggedness salient.

- "I selected this robot for the construction site task because of its efficiency, durability, and ability to handle heavy materials in challenging environments." (White, Dark robot, Construction, L3)
- "They seem like it would be tough and able to handle rough sports activities." (Asian, Dark robot, Sports, L2)
- "It has well-build design to withstand running." (Black/African American, Brown robot, Sports, L5)
- "I selected this robot because it does not have a fancy color and its basic. In a construction site it won't ruin the type of paint/color it has." (Latino/Hispanic, Silver robot, Construction, L1)

b) *1.2 Cleanliness & Maintenance* ($N = 222$, 3.8%): Participants focused on how the robot's color interacts with environmental cleanliness—either hiding dirt in messy settings or signaling sterility in clinical ones. This sub-category peaked in hospital (6.8%) and construction (5.7%) contexts, reflecting the contrasting cleanliness demands of these environments.

- “I pick the white robot since it is the hospital setting. For me, having a white robot is fit in the hospital that focus on cleanliness so if the robot is dirty it can be easily clean and spot the dirt.” (Asian, Light robot, Hospital, L1)
- “Because I believe the color brown is more suitable for construction site since the color brown is not easy to notice dirt and the color of sand is usually brown.” (Asian, Brown robot, Construction, L1)
- “In a sterile environment like a hospital people would like a shiny looking robot.” (Latino/Hispanic, Silver robot, Hospital, L2)
- “Since it’s a hospital setting, a white robot will help users see how clean it is.” (White, Light robot, Hospital, L3)

c) 1.3 Visibility & Safety ($N = 680, 11.7\%$): Participants cited the practical need for the robot to be easily seen by humans to prevent accidents or enable tracking. This sub-category was dominant in construction (24.5%) due to safety concerns and elevated in sports (16.9%).

- “I chose a robot color that’s more visible so it can be spotted easily, for its safety.” (Asian, Dark robot, Construction, L2)
- “I selected that robot because I believe it should be a stronger color for safety reasons. The other colors seem like they might not stand out enough.” (Latino/Hispanic, Teal robot, Construction, L5)
- “I think this color would be best for students to have it highlighted in the class room setting.” (Latino/Hispanic, Teal robot, Tutoring, L2)
- “I would choose this robot mainly because of visibility.” (White, Teal robot, Construction, L2)

d) 1.4 Professionalism & Contextual Fit ($N = 1,238, 21.2\%$): The single most frequent sub-category, in which participants matched the robot’s appearance to the typical aesthetics of a specific industry or environment. This sub-category peaked in hospital (29.0%) and sports (23.1%) contexts, where occupational norms were most salient.

- “The color of this robot resembles healthcare and it would be the best for this role.” (Asian, Light robot, Hospital, L5)
- “I think the color matched the scrubs of a nurse. Blue is a softer color appropriate for a hospital setting.” (Latino/Hispanic, Teal robot, Hospital, L5)
- “I think the reason I selected this robot is because he looks like he would fit in a construction site.” (Black/African American, Dark robot, Construction, L2)
- “Something about the darker color of this robot made me think it would be better suited in construction.” (White, Dark robot, Construction, L3)

e) 1.5 Performance/Capability ($N = 736, 12.6\%$): Participants made general attributions of skill, accuracy, or efficiency based on the robot’s appearance. This sub-category was most prevalent in sports (19.7%) where athletic competence was emphasized.

- “The blue color makes it look extra intelligent.” (Asian, Teal robot, Tutoring, L5)
- “I chose this robot for the hospital task because it is reliable, precise, and capable of assisting medical staff efficiently.” (Black/African American, Medium robot, Hospital, L5)
- “It looked the boldest, so I felt like it would be the most capable.” (Latino/Hispanic, Dark robot, Construction, L3)
- “He seems to be intelligent and helpful.” (Black/African American, Brown robot, Tutoring, L2)

B. Category 2: Psych/Affective

Justifications in this category are based on the emotional response the robot elicits in the target audience. This was the second most common framework (22.0%), with dramatic context dependence—dominant in hospital and tutoring and nearly absent in physical labor contexts.

a) 2.1 Approachability & Trust ($N = 819, 14.1\%$): Participants perceived the robot as non-threatening, kind, or welcoming to humans. This was the most context-dependent sub-category, serving as the dominant reasoning in hospital (29.7%) and tutoring (22.7%) but dropping to near absence in construction (1.5%) and sports (2.3%).

- “The appearance seems friendly and more personable.” (Asian, Teal robot, Hospital, L2)
- “It appears that it could offer compassion and be there in a manner of sympathy.” (Black/African American, Medium robot, Hospital, L2)
- “The light blue robot color was positive, so I felt like it would be best for an emotional support robot.” (Latino/Hispanic, Teal robot, Hospital, L3)
- “A lighter colored robot would probably be viewed as more approachable to students.” (White, Light robot, Tutoring, L3)

b) 2.2 Engagement & Animation ($N = 339, 5.8\%$): Participants believed that the colors would motivate users or maintain their attention. This sub-category was uniquely elevated in tutoring (12.7%—more than double any other task), reflecting concern for capturing children’s attention.

- “I chose a robot with a cheerful color to hopefully improve patient’s mood.” (Asian, Teal robot, Hospital, L2)
- “I chose this robot because the aqua blue tone is more of a positive, uplifting color.” (Black/African American, Teal robot, Hospital, L3)

- *“It looks like it would be appealing to a child.”* (Latino/Hispanic, Light robot, Tutoring, L1)
- *“I chose the blue robot because I assume it’s mostly children that will be tutored, and they might enjoy the bright color.”* (White, Teal robot, Tutoring, L3)

c) 2.3 *Human-Likeness / Social* ($N = 124$, 2.1%): Participants explicitly chose a robot because it looked “more human” or had a skin tone appropriate for social interaction. This sub-category showed the most dramatic response to human-likeness manipulation, rising thirty-fold from 0.2% at Level 1 to 6.3% at Level 5.

- *“This looks the most humanlike and will fit in in a hospital setting.”* (Asian, Light robot, Hospital, L5)
- *“Its complexion is like that of a human being.”* (Black/African American, Brown robot, Construction, L5)
- *“Slightly human like color so as to provide some extra comfort and warmth.”* (Latino/Hispanic, Light robot, Hospital, L5)
- *“I picked this one because it’s slightly more lifelike, which is better for a more personalized experience.”* (White, Light robot, Tutoring, L5)

C. Category 3: Machine-Centric

Justifications in this category emphasize the robot’s status as an industrial tool, often to avoid social or racial complications. This category accounted for 9.8% of responses and was overwhelmingly associated with non-skin-tone robot selections. It nearly doubled from 8.2% at the lowest human-likeness level to 16.2% at the highest.

a) 3.1 *Materiality & Industrialism* ($N = 169$, 2.9%): Participants associated robot colors with raw materials like metal, steel, or plastic, framing the robot as an industrial artifact rather than a social agent.

- *“I chose the most ‘conventional’ looking robot by color, as color was the only distinguishing characteristic among the robots.”* (Asian, Silver robot, Construction, L3)
- *“I selected the robot because of the color. Construction machines don’t require aesthetics.”* (Black/African American, Silver robot, Construction, L2)
- *“The grey makes it look the most utilitarian which I associate with construction.”* (Latino/Hispanic, Silver robot, Construction, L1)
- *“It looks like what you’d expect a robot to look like.”* (White, Silver robot, Hospital, L3)

b) 3.2 *Neutrality & De-racialization* ($N = 249$, 4.3%): Participants explicitly stated that robots should not have human skin tones, choosing a color to be “neutral” or to avoid racial implications. This sub-category rose five-fold from 2.2% at Level 1 to 10.8% at Level 5, with Asian participants invoking this reasoning at nearly four times the rate of Black/African American participants.

- *“I thought a neutral color tone would be best so that it would elicit the least reaction based on the color.”* (Asian, Light robot, Construction, L1)
- *“In a politically correct world, someone might be offended if the robot was ‘white’. I figured that this is a color compromise.”* (Black/African American, Medium robot, Tutoring, L5)
- *“Neutral color so the workers see it as what it is, a robot supervisor.”* (Latino/Hispanic, Silver robot, Construction, L5)
- *“I did not want a racial bias.”* (White, Silver robot, Construction, L4)

c) 3.3 *Anti-Distraction* ($N = 154$, 2.6%): Participants chose a “boring” or “basic” color so that the user would focus on the task rather than the robot. This sub-category was most elevated in tutoring (5.9%), reflecting concern about maintaining students’ focus on learning.

- *“I selected the beige colored robot because it is a neutral and inoffensive color that would not stick out nor draw too much attention.”* (Asian, Medium robot, Hospital, L4)
- *“The robot’s color scheme is unobtrusive, appears as though it would minimize distraction in the workplace.”* (Black/African American, Medium robot, Construction, L5)
- *“This robot has a muted and non-distracting color for studying students.”* (Latino/Hispanic, Medium robot, Tutoring, L4)
- *“The color isn’t too distracting so that the people being tutored wouldn’t be distracted by that, and could focus on the material.”* (White, Silver robot, Tutoring, L2)

D. Category 4: Preference/Evasion

Low-effort or purely subjective justifications in which participants either expressed simple personal preferences or acknowledged that their choice was arbitrary. This category accounted for 14.2% of responses and was characterized by shorter average word counts than other categories.

a) 4.1 *Personal Aesthetic* ($N = 530, 9.1\%$): Simple statements of personal liking or attraction to a color without further elaboration on task fit or functional rationale.

- “No particular reason as they are all the same—I liked the color.” (Asian, Light robot, Construction, L1)
- “I like its color, really.” (Black/African American, Silver robot, Construction, L5)
- “I like the color on the robot, nothing else was different from all of them besides the color.” (Latino/Hispanic, Teal robot, Construction, L2)
- “I liked the color of the robot.” (White, Light robot, Construction, L4)

b) 4.2 *Random/Equivalence* ($N = 298, 5.1\%$): Participants admitted the choice was arbitrary or that all robots seemed functionally identical, rendering color irrelevant to their decision.

- “I chose randomly as they all look the same.” (Asian, Brown robot, Construction, L5)
- “Because of color since they all look alike.” (Black/African American, Teal robot, Hospital, L4)
- “I just followed my intuitions.” (Latino/Hispanic, Silver robot, Hospital, L5)
- “Since they all looked alike I made a random choice.” (White, Light robot, Tutoring, L4)

E. Category 5: Identity/Social

Justifications that reveal underlying social mapping or identity projection onto the robot. Though the rarest category (1.0% of responses), it provides direct evidence of stereotype transfer from human social categories to robotic agents. These responses were overwhelmingly associated with skin-tone robot selections (84.5%).

a) 5.1 *Stereotype Alignment* ($N = 51, 0.9\%$): Participants chose a robot color based on their belief that the chosen color matches the typical, common, or expected human demographic of a specific profession. This sub-category was most prevalent in sports (1.9%) and construction (1.3%), and nearly absent in hospital (0.1%).

- “Its tan so it doesn’t get dirtied as much as the light ones. It is also the stereotype too of brown skin in construction are better at it than other skin color.” (Asian, Brown robot, Construction, L1)
- “Anything but a white robot. We have too much white leadership in society.” (Black/African American, Dark robot, Hospital, L3)
- “Well the workers are usually minorities, so it would not be fair to put the robot white.” (Latino/Hispanic, Medium robot, Construction, L5)
- “I think the color white may imply it’s smart? Like the way you assume people in white lab coats are smart.” (White, Light robot, Tutoring, L1)

b) 5.2 *Identity Projection* ($N = 7, 0.1\%$): A small but revealing subset in which participants explicitly chose a robot that mirrors their own personal characteristics, extending their self-concept to include robotic agents.

- “It is black like me and it looks strong.” (Black/African American, Dark robot, Construction, L5)
- “It’s just a reflection of myself.” (Asian, Brown robot, Tutoring, L1)
- “I chose the robot because it reflected my thoughts and how I feel.” (Latino/Hispanic, Teal robot, Construction, L2)

IV. PRIMING AND COLOR SELECTION

Figure 3 provides a detailed comparison of justification category distributions between the priming and no-priming conditions. As established in the main text, the presence of racial priming did not significantly alter the reasoning frameworks participants employed ($\chi^2(4) = 8.29, p = .081$). This stability across conditions reinforces the dual-process model interpretation, wherein deliberative justifications provide post-hoc rationalizations for decisions influenced by implicit associations.

V. JUSTIFICATION CATEGORIES BY PARTICIPANT RACE

Figure 4 details the distribution of justification categories across the four primary participant racial groups. While **Functionalism** and **Psych/Affective** reasoning dominated across all groups, the figure highlights demographic variations, such as Asian participants employing higher rates of **Machine-Centric** reasoning (primarily driven by de-racialization rationales) compared to other demographic groups.

Figure 5 provides a more granular view of these demographic variations at the sub-category level.

Fig. 3. Distribution of main justification categories by priming condition. The proportions remain broadly consistent between the Prime and No-Prime groups, indicating that while priming shifts selection behavior, it does not rewrite the underlying reasoning narratives.

Fig. 4. Proportion of justification categories by participant race. Each bar shows the distribution of reasoning frameworks for a given racial group.

Fig. 5. Sub-category proportions (%) within each participant racial group. Darker shading indicates higher proportions within a given race.